

THE STUDY OF WORKS OF THE GENRE OF ANECDOTES IN WORLD FOLKLORE AND THE IMPORTANCE OF ANECDOTES FOR TODAY

Mardonov Maxmud Sobir ugli

Researcher, Navoi State University of Mining and Technology

gmail: mmaxmud1992@gmail.com

Annotation. *Since ancient times, man has expressed his reaction to the events taking place in the environment. This relationship was realized primarily through various actions, voices, and passions. Later, words, phrases, and dances expressed feelings. Later, people will come up with their own woven stories explaining the appearance of the world, nature, animals, plants, mountains, and water. Boys and girls sing love songs. Anecdotes, those short, humorous tales designed to provoke laughter and amusement, are more than just amusing stories. They are powerful windows into the soul of a culture, reflecting its values, beliefs, social norms, and everyday life. They are a cornerstone of world folklore, passed down through generations, evolving and adapting to changing times. This article delves into the study of anecdotes in world folklore, exploring their historical significance, diverse forms, and their enduring relevance in today's world.*

Key words: *basics of folklore studies, collection and analysis, historical development of anecdotes, strengthening of cultural unity, methods of studying anecdotes.*

Introduction. Today, we are used to calling them "folk art". That is why it was customary to call folk art as national values. Folk art is called folklore in science. This term was proposed by the English scientist William Thoms in 1846, and its meaning consists of the concept of "people's wisdom". Basically, folklore means all the art examples created by the people. Examples of architecture, painting, jewelry, goldsmithing, music, dance, oral literature - all of them are accepted as folklore. Anecdotes are an important part of folklore, they reflect the history, traditions, customs, values and way of life of a society. The study of the anecdote genre in world folklore reveals a lot about folk art, culture and society. Anecdotes are still relevant today, they help people laugh, overcome stress, discuss socio-political issues and preserve cultural wealth.

The Study of Anecdotes in World Folklore: A Rich Tapestry

1. Anecdotes as a Genre:

o Anecdotes are considered a distinct genre of folklore, categorized alongside myths, legends, folktales, and proverbs. They are distinguished by their brevity, focus on a specific event or situation, and the presence of humor.

o Anecdotes often involve relatable characters, often ordinary individuals facing everyday situations or engaging in witty banter. This makes them easily accessible and relatable across cultures.

2. The Role of Folklore Studies:

o Folklore studies play a crucial role in understanding and preserving anecdotes. Researchers gather, analyze, and interpret these narratives, uncovering their underlying themes, cultural significance, and historical context.

o By collecting anecdotes from diverse communities and time periods, folklorists create a comprehensive picture of human experience and cultural expressions.

3. Methods of Studying Anecdotes:

o **Collection and Analysis:** Anecdotes are collected through oral traditions, written sources, and archival research. They are then analyzed for their structural elements, themes, and cultural context.

o **Comparative Analysis:** Comparing anecdotes from different cultures allows researchers to identify shared themes and patterns, as well as cultural variations in humor and storytelling styles.

o **Contextual Interpretation:** Understanding the historical, social, and cultural context of anecdotes is vital to interpret their meaning and significance.

Historical Evolution of Anecdotes: A Journey Through Time

1. Ancient Origins:

o Anecdotes have ancient roots, appearing in oral traditions across cultures. Early civilizations like the Egyptians, Greeks, and Romans documented humorous stories and anecdotes in their literature and art.

o Ancient Greek philosophers like Plato used anecdotes to illustrate philosophical concepts, demonstrating their pedagogical value.

o Roman satirists like Petronius and Juvenal employed anecdotes to expose societal flaws and vices through humor.

2. Medieval and Renaissance Periods:

o During the Middle Ages, anecdotes became popular vehicles for moral instruction and social commentary. They often featured religious figures, saints, or wise men as protagonists.

o The Renaissance saw a resurgence of interest in classical literature, leading to the collection and translation of ancient anecdotes.

3. The Enlightenment and Beyond:

o The Enlightenment emphasized reason and wit, contributing to the development of the modern anecdote as a form of intellectual humor.

o Literary figures like Samuel Johnson and Voltaire skillfully incorporated anecdotes into their writings, highlighting their ability to entertain and provoke thought.

The Enduring Importance of Anecdotes: A Mirror to Our Times

1. Social Commentary and Satire:

o Anecdotes often serve as a platform for social commentary, poking fun at societal norms, political figures, or human foibles.

o They can highlight inequalities, expose hypocrisy, and challenge authority through humor.

2. Cultural Identity and Values:

o Anecdotes reveal a culture's values, beliefs, and traditions. They often feature local characters, customs, and humor specific to a particular group or region.

- o They provide insights into how people perceive themselves and their place in the world.

3. Sharing Experience and Connecting People:

- o Anecdotes are a powerful way to share experiences and connect with others. They can be used to build relationships, foster camaraderie, and promote understanding.

- o The relatable nature of anecdotes allows people from different backgrounds to laugh together and forge common ground.

4. Language and Communication:

- o Anecdotes showcase the richness and creativity of language. They often employ wordplay, puns, and subtle humor, demonstrating the power of language to entertain and enlighten.

Anecdotes in the Digital Age: New Forms and Platforms

1. The Rise of Online Humor:

- o The internet and social media have revolutionized the spread and consumption of anecdotes. Online platforms have become breeding grounds for viral jokes, memes, and humorous stories.

- o Social media allows anecdotes to transcend geographical boundaries, reaching audiences across the globe.

2. New Forms of Storytelling:

- o With the emergence of new technologies, anecdotes have taken on innovative forms. Videos, animated GIFs, and interactive storytelling platforms have become popular ways to share and experience humor.

- o The rise of stand-up comedy and the accessibility of online platforms have provided new avenues for storytellers to share their experiences and perspectives through humor.

3. Humor in a Globalized World:

- o In a world increasingly interconnected, anecdotes bridge cultural gaps and promote understanding. They can help us laugh at our shared humanity and appreciate the diversity of human experience.

- o However, it's crucial to be mindful of cultural differences and avoid perpetuating stereotypes or offensive humor.

The first examples of myths related to the past life of the peoples living in Central Asia are given in the book "Avesta". "Avesta" is the creation of our ancestors who lived in ancient Khorezm. The work, which first appeared orally, was written in golden letters on 12,000 black cattle skins at the initiative of Zoroaster after the formation of the writing culture. Legends of the 11th century are recorded in the books called "Kitobi Dada Korqut" and "Oguznoma" about Oguz Kogon who lived in the 13th century (although the events in them indicate that the text of the legends was created much earlier, in the scientific works of the 11th and 13th century) contained mythical representations of the history of Turkic tribes and clans. If the events that cannot happen in legends are narrated, the events in the narratives often tell about specific episodes in the lives of historical figures, famous scholars, and statesmen. Sometimes when we hear a story, we fully believe that it happened, sometimes we may not believe

the story, even if it is free from a special fantastic image. Therefore, it is difficult to define a sharp difference between legend and narrative. In any case, based on many years of experience, it can be said that it is appropriate to accept a story that is believed as a legend, and one that cannot be believed as a myth. Because there is no difference between legends and narratives in terms of content and plot system. Only narrations are considered to be historical evidence, evidence. Another type of narratives is distinguished by the names of places in local areas. The important thing is that in such narratives, the focus is not on the fantastic aspects of the described story, but on the qualities of observing life, coming to the right conclusions, and using the mind.

The following conclusions can be drawn from the opinions expressed about the narratives:

1. Stories, unlike legends, are based on real-life events.
2. They are thematically divided into types and either describe an important event in the life of a historical person or explain the name of a geographical place.
3. In narratives, more attention is paid to describing the event in a short and concise, simple and fluent manner than in artistic depiction. In fact, it is precisely these qualities that determine the artistic nature of narratives.

Zarbulmasal is an Arabic word that means to hit (criticize) the guilty with a parable. Muhammad Jobalrudi (XVII century) used this word as synonyms of parable and parable, and in another place he gave it in the sense of a symbolic story. In "Ghiyos ul-lugat" it is defined as the carrier of one or another figurative meaning in speech. In Uzbek folk prose, it is called a parable. Zarbulmasal was originally a separate genre of written literature. It was later referred to as a parable.

These genres are close to each other, they are equaled by figurative meaning, allegory. So, the metaphorical meaning is a general, at the same time, the main and decisive sign for proverbs, sayings, parables, proverbs, and riddles. A proverb is basically a set of wise thoughts and teachings. Therefore, it is a story that creates philosophical generalizations from life events and events, and describes exemplary behavior and behavior in a metaphorical way. So, the proverb glorifies intelligence, manners, and wisdom, and allows understanding and evaluation.

The term naqil and naql are very common in Uzbek classic literature and folklore works. One is a teller, a narrator, and the other means a story. Initially, stories, proverbs, fairy tales, proverbs, riddles, epics were also referred to as narratives. Narrator means someone who tells a story about morals and etiquette norms that are worthy of example.

Conclusion. Anecdotes, with their simple yet profound power to make us laugh and reflect, are an essential part of world folklore. They serve as a timeless reflection of human nature, societal values, and cultural diversity. By studying anecdotes, we gain valuable insights into the past, present, and future of human experience. As we navigate an increasingly complex world, the ability to share and appreciate humor remains a vital tool for connection, understanding, and positive change.

References:

1. "The Study of Folklore" by Alan Dundes
2. "The Encyclopedia of World Folklore" by D.L. Ashliman
3. "Anecdotes: A Collection of Humorous Tales" by Various Authors
4. "The Power of Laughter: Why Humor Matters in Our Lives" by Steve Allen
5. "The Art of Storytelling" by Robert McKee
6. "The History of Humor" by John Morreall
7. "Humor and the Brain" by Daniel Goleman